

NEW PROOFS IN MODERN GRAVITATION THEORY

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Neutrino basis of attraction and repulsion of magnets

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New proofs in modern gravitation theory

IV part

Neutrino basis of attraction and repulsion of magnets

Annotation: The carrier of the magnetic wave is the neutrino. Magnetic waves arise as a result of vibrations of the electron shell of the atom, whose vibrations are transmitted to the interatomic electron neutrino. As a result of the experiment with permanent magnets, the limitation of the neutrino flux from the Earth's core was established. The attraction and repulsion of permanent magnets is explained by the interaction of countercurrent neutrino flows. Under the influence of external anomalous zones formed between the magnetic fields of permanent magnets, neutrino fluxes acquire the property of narrowing and expanding.

Keywords: neutrino and magnetic field, magnet attraction effect,

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Abstract: The carrier of a magnetic wave and how a magnetic field arises has not yet been established by science. In this work, the author proposes a logical model, supported by experimental data, for determining the mechanism of attraction and repulsion of magnets. The nature of the magnetic field is based on the movement of the neutrino wave and the properties of a permanent magnet to collect or expand the fluxes of the neutrino wave.

According to the results of the experiment with permanent magnets, the limitation of the neutrino flux from the Earth's core was established. The attraction and repulsion of permanent magnets is explained by the interaction of countercurrent neutrino flows in the magnet. Under the influence of external anomalous zones formed between the magnetic fields of permanent magnets, neutrino flows acquire the property of narrowing and expanding. As a result, a potential difference between the penetrating neutrino flows appears between the magnets, which, depending on the method of applying the poles of permanent magnets, forms the effect of attraction or repulsion of the magnets. The anomalous zones between the magnetic fields contribute to a change in the direction of neutrino movement, due to which the neutrino flux acquires the ability to change its density level.

Neutrino waves are magnetic waves. Magnetic waves do not tend to affect other bodies and particles. Magnetic waves only affect neutrinos. As a result, neutrinos under the influence of magnetic waves exert pressure on other particles, atoms and bodies.

In this paper, from this point of view, an explanation is given for many effects that manifest themselves between magnets and do not have a logical explanation. Research work is intended for scientists, students and pupils.

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Introduction

Paradoxically, modern physics still does not know what a “magnetic field” is in the literal sense: its nature, carrier particle, interaction mechanism, and how it is formed.

The origin of the Earth's magnetic field remains a mystery to scientists, although there are many hypotheses to explain this phenomenon. The magnetic field that exists on the earth's surface is a total field formed by a number of sources: the first is the currents crossing the earth's surface, the so-called "vortex" field; the second - external, cosmic sources not connected with the Earth, and, finally, the third - the magnetic field due to the causes of thermodynamo. This last source makes the greatest contribution to the formation of the geomagnetic field, and most of the hypotheses are devoted to its genesis.[1]

In the treatise of William Gilbert, the court physician of the English Queen Elizabeth I, "On the magnet, magnetic bodies and the large magnet - the Earth", which was published in 1600, it is shown that the Earth's magnetic field is the same as that of

a magnetic dipole, that is, our the planet is like a big magnetic needle. Anticipating the last book of his famous treatise with parting words, Gilbert wrote: “Now we should reveal the causes and surprising, although previously noticed, but unexplained effects of all this.” After 400 years, Gilbert's words still have not lost their relevance.[2]

James Clerk Maxwell, in his treatise *On Electricity and Magnetism*, discussing the theory of magnetism (item 832), writes that the action of magnets on each other can be exactly represented by the attraction and repulsion of an imaginary substance called magnetic matter. We have come to Poisson's hypothesis that magnetic matter is concentrated strictly in individual molecules of magnetic matter. In paragraph 833, Maxwell states that, nevertheless, we still have not arrived at any explanation of the nature of the magnetic molecule. We have not yet found its resemblance to any other thing better known to us. Therefore, we should consider Ampere's hypothesis that the magnetism of a molecule is due to an electric current constantly circulating along some closed path inside the molecule. These currents must circulate within the molecules of the magnet and must not flow from one molecule to another.[3]

Meanwhile, modern physics cannot explain what even a permanent magnet or a magnetic field is in the physical sense. The carrier of the magnetic field has not been determined. We often explain the property of a magnet philosophically, as an obvious phenomenon. However, as soon as the question arises about the mechanism of attraction and repulsion of magnets, the physics of a magnet becomes a mystery.

For this reason, one of the mysterious phenomena in nature remains the property of attraction between permanent magnets. When two magnets with different poles approach, they attract, and with the same poles, they repel. We erroneously attribute these properties of a magnet to the influence of a magnetic field, although everyone knows that a magnetic field in itself does not have the property of physical interaction with material bodies, let alone attraction. This is not difficult to verify. Take a piece of a permanent magnet and attach it to bodies made of various materials: wood, plastic, aluminum, iron, and others. The magnet attracts only iron or iron-containing metals, while the magnet remains indifferent to other bodies, although the magnetic field of the magnet was preserved everywhere.

In this work, the carrier of the magnetic field and the nature of its occurrence are determined. Here the magnetic field is considered as the main factor influencing the properties of gravity. To this end, we will study a simple permanent magnet and its ability to change the direction of neutrino movement and establish how intense sections of the magnetic field affect the rectilinear motion of these elementary particles.

I. Screening of neutrino fluxes by the Earth's core

1.1. Limitation of neutrino fluxes from the Earth's core

*To prove a scientific position, thousands of facts are needed,
and to refute, one is enough.* *Ualikhan Adayev*

In 2005, the KamLAND experiment (the only existing neutrino detector capable of capturing the neutrino flux from the Earth's core) managed to detect electron antineutrinos emitted during the beta decay of uranium-238 and thorium-232 from the surface of the Earth's core.

According to "PhysicsWeb", the results of data processing obtained by the KamLAND detector showed that about 16.2 million neutrinos are "born" on the surface of the Earth's core per 1 cm² per second on the Earth's surface. [4]

Ultra-low energy neutrinos from space vacuum in a volume of 10⁷ - 10⁸ (ν)/cm² sec are absorbed in beta-minus decay on the surface of the Earth's central core and radiate from the Earth's core in the order of 10⁶ (ν)/cm²sec towards the Earth's surface. The difference in absorbed neutrino exerts a mechanical pressure due to the lack of energy exchange.

The difference in the neutrino flux will be the absence of energy exchange:

$$\nu_{\beta^-} - \nu_{\beta^+} = \sim 10^7 - 10^8 (\nu + \bar{\nu})/\text{cm}^2\text{сек} - 10^6 (\bar{\nu})/\text{cm}^2\text{сек} = \sim 10^1 - 10^2 (\nu + \bar{\nu})/\text{cm}^2\text{сек}$$

As a result, only the central core of the planet shields the all-penetrating neutrino flux.[5]

According to the model of gravity formation proposed in this theory, the movement of the neutrino flow is directed to the surface of the central core of the Earth, where they stop their movement. However, the central core of our planet is not a point and has a diameter of 2500 km. This circumstance is directly reflected in the characteristics of neutrino fluxes.

As shown in figure 1.1, on the surface of the Earth, the streams of neutrinos \mathbf{v}_B , \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_n , directed at certain angles, create a general gravitational pressure on the surface of our planet. In addition to the vertical neutrino flux \mathbf{v}_B , the remaining \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_n are components of oblique gravitational fluxes. The latter flows are mutually balanced in a symmetrical form, since they are directed at the same angles from the vertical flow and generally create a total pressure in one direction.

The angle of oblique neutrino fluxes (fig. 1.1) can be approximately calculated using the following formula:

$$\varphi = r / R$$

where r - is the radius of the inner core, R - is the radius of the Earth, φ -is the sine of the angle of oblique flows.

$$\varphi_1 = 1250000 \text{ M} / 6378000 \text{ M} = 0,196 = 11,3^\circ,$$

from here on the entire surface of the inner core we get 22.6° .

On the Earth's surface, the level of influence of gravity density is 9.81 m/s^2 , which corresponds to 22.6° of inclined flows. отсюда на всю поверхность внутреннего ядра получим $22,6^\circ$.

Thus, the central core of the Earth shields the neutrino flows, as a result of which the earth's gravitational attraction is formed. In this case, experiments with magnets can be used to test the limitation of neutrino fluxes from the Earth's core.

The fact is that the effect of attraction and repulsion of permanent magnets is considered in this paper as a force formed under the influence of neutrinos on magnets. During the experiment, it is necessary to establish that the attraction and repulsion of two magnets created by neutrino flows in the horizontal plane must be greater than the force of attraction and repulsion of the same magnets in a vertical position. To calculate the indicated difference in the forces of attraction and repulsion of permanent magnets,

two permanent square magnets with sides of 26 mm and a thickness of 9 mm were used in the experiment.

In these positions of the magnets, as shown in Figures 1.2 and 1.3, we obtain the difference in the interaction of neutrinos directed in two planes. As stated above, in the vertical plane from the side of the central core of the Earth, the neutrino flux has some limitation, screened by the central core of our planet. The purpose of our experiment is to determine the volume of the shielded neutrino flux as a percentage, since an important role in the experiments is played by the magnetic constant, which

characterizes the power of the magnetic field of the magnet.

First, in a horizontal position, we measure the weight of the load, which causes two adhered magnets to come off (A in Fig. 1.2). In this position, the magnet breaks off only due to the force generated by the weight of the load ($F = m$

g). The detachment of adhered magnets in a horizontal position requires a mass $m_1 = 985g$, and to overcome the repulsive force (B in Fig. 1.2) - $m_3 = 1335g$. In a vertical position (A in Fig. 1.3), the weight of the falling magnet itself, 40 g, is added to the weight of the load. ($F=(m+m_m)g$). Measurement of weights in cases of sticking and repulsion of vertical magnets gives the following readings

$$m_2 = m + m_m = 760 + 40 = 800g,$$

$$m_4 = m + m_m = 1110 + 40 = 1150g.$$

The mass difference in both positions of the magnets is 185g.

From here we calculate the forces acting on the magnets by attraction:

$$F_1 = m_1 g = 985 g \cdot 9,81 m/s^2 = 9663 g m/s^2$$

$$F_2 = m_2 g = 800 g \cdot 9,81 m/s^2 = 7848 g m/s^2$$

The repulsive forces acting on the magnets are:

$$F_3 = m_3 g = 1335 g \cdot 9,81 m/s^2 = 13096 g m/s^2$$

$$F_4 = m_4 g = 1150 g \cdot 9,81 m/s^2 = 11281 g m/s^2$$

The difference between these forces, in the horizontal and vertical positions, will give the difference that is formed as a result of a decrease in the volume of neutrino fluxes from the Earth's core.

For detachment of adhered magnets, this difference is equal to:

$$F_1 - F_2 = 9663 \text{ g m/s}^2 - 7848 \text{ g m/s}^2 = 1815 \text{ g m/s}^2$$

To overcome the repulsion of magnets, this difference is equal to:

$$F_3 - F_4 = 13096 \text{ g m/s}^2 - 11281 \text{ g m/s}^2 = 1815 \text{ g m/s}^2$$

In both cases, the force difference

$$\mathbf{F1 - F2 = F3 - F4 = F = 1815 \text{ g m/s}^2.}$$

It should be noted that with a magnet mass of 40 grams, the difference in the mass of the load in the vertical and horizontal positions of 185 grams exceeds 4.6 times.

This difference is given by two magnets with a volume of 26 mm each · 26 mm · 9 mm = 6084mm³.

From here it is not difficult to calculate the difference in forces on magnets with a volume 1 cm³ or 1000 mm³. She is equal $F = 298,3 \text{ g m/s}^2$.

So we got the difference in the impact of neutrinos directed in vertical and horizontal planes for this type of magnet.

$$\mathbf{F = 298,3 \text{ g m/s}^2.}$$

As stated above, on the surface of the Earth, the level of influence of gravity density is 9,81 m/s², which corresponds to 22.6° of oblique flows towards the core of the planet. Accordingly, the neutrino flux from the side of the Earth's core arrives at the magnet by 22.6° degrees less than towards the core of our planet.

This means that if the cosmic neutrino flux puts pressure on the magnets from above (P_k) from all over 180° surface, from below this pressure (P_i) is less by 22.6° (red dotted triangle in Figure 1.3). As a percentage, this is equal to:

$$P_i = 180^\circ, \quad P_i = 180^\circ - 22,6^\circ = 157,4^\circ, \quad \text{from here:}$$

$$X = \frac{P_{\text{я}} \mathbf{100\%}}{P_k} = \frac{\mathbf{157,4^0 \cdot 100\%}}{\mathbf{180^0}} = \mathbf{87,44\%} \quad \text{from the core of the earth.}$$

Cosmic neutrino stream from above - 100%, then

$$100\% - 87,44\% = 12,56\%,$$

that is, the amount of neutrino flow directed from bottom to top and acting on the magnet is **12.56%** less than the amount of neutrino flow going from top to bottom.

In a horizontal arrangement of magnets, the position of the plane of application of the pressure of the neutrino flows will change, and the influence of the neutrino flow coming from the Earth's core will change accordingly. In this case, the neutrino flux

from below will bifurcate and act on each magnet only halfway, that is, 11.3° (red dotted triangle in Figure 1.2).

Let's try to calculate this difference.

At 12.56%, the difference of forces was calculated, which is equal to $F = 298.3 \text{ g m/s}^2$. From here we calculate the average force equal to one percent:

At 12.56%, the difference of forces was calculated, which is equal to $F = 298.3 \text{ g m/s}^2$. From here we calculate the average force equal to one percent:

$$F_{\text{average percentage}} = \frac{298,3 \text{ g m/s}^2}{12,56\%} = 23,75 \text{ g m/s}^2.$$

In the same way, we calculate the average force equal to one degree:

$$F_{\text{average degree.}} = \frac{F}{22,6^\circ} = \frac{298,3 \text{ g m/s}^2}{22,6^\circ} = 13,20 \text{ g m/s}^2.$$

However, it will be fair if we take into account that in the horizontal position of the magnets, they are also affected by a limited difference in the forces of attraction from the Earth's core, which is equal to half - 11.3° . Then,

$$F = \frac{F_{\text{average degree.}}}{2} = \frac{13,20 \text{ g m/s}^2}{2} = 6,6 \text{ g m/s}^2.$$

Calculations of the properties of permanent magnets have shown that from the side of the Earth's core, the neutrino flux with a volume $F_{av} = 298.3 \text{ g m/s}^2$, acting on

one cubic centimeter of this type of permanent magnet, is reduced. This stream of neutrinos limited from below creates an effect of attraction on the surface of the Earth.

In general, any body on the surface of our planet is affected by a limited neutrino flux from the Earth's core, the volume of which is equal to 12.56% of the total volume of neutrino fluxes acting on the body.

The results of the experiment indicate that the effect of attraction and repulsion of magnets is strictly related to the influence of neutrino flows, since it gives a noticeable difference in vertical and horizontal planes. It is impossible to explain this experiment without the influence of neutrino fluxes. The flow of neutrinos from the side of the Earth's core is limited, as a result of which an attraction is formed on the Earth's surface.

Also, this experiment indicates that the magnetic field is formed by waves of the neutrino flux.

II. Special properties of the magnetic field

2.1. Nature of magnetic field interaction

Each magnet is surrounded by a magnetic field. Magnetic forces can be detected around each magnet. These forces are caused by the magnetic field surrounding the magnet. This magnetic field affects other magnets - magnetic materials or moving charged particles. By itself, the magnetic field does not affect other bodies. The magnitude of the force or strength of the magnetic field varies with distance from the magnet, but is always greatest at the poles of the magnet. The magnetic field at the pole of an artificial magnet is usually hundreds of times stronger than the Earth's magnetic field. In nature, there are anomalous zones in a magnetic field, which is associated with an increased or decreased level of magnetic wave density.

The main properties of magnets are manifested by the interaction of two magnets. Only another magnet with the same pole can be repelled by a magnet. Exactly such properties are manifested in the interaction of inductive coils.

But how does it happen? What is the reason for such a property of a magnet, more precisely, a magnetic field? Do not such properties of a magnet indicate that the reason for the attraction and repulsion of magnets lies in a completely different force? Isn't a magnet a conductor of completely different interactions, which, being transformed in a magnet, create a force? If so, then what force in nature can claim to be the creator of the attraction and repulsion effects of magnets? Let's try to look at this problem from the point of view of neutrino interaction.

2.2. External and internal anomalous zones of magnetic fields

A permanent magnet creates a spatial magnetic field around itself, the property of which depends on the shape of the magnet: sphere, cube, prism, cylinder and parallelepiped.

A magnet can be influenced by many fields of elementary particles, such as gravity, heat, electric current, inertia, acceleration, acting and passing through the body of the magnet. Of the listed forces, only gravity acts on the magnet constantly, and the rest of the forces - only when applied. For this reason, let's take the neutrino (ν) as the main driving force of the magnet of the gravitational carrier.

As shown in Figure 2.1, magnetic field carriers actively interact with each other. With a parallel or sequential direction (**A**), they merge and can affect elementary particles, orienting them through the density of the magnetic field. In this case, in the central section between the magnets along the axis, an external anomalous zone of the magnetic field with an increased level of intensity is formed. As a result, two magnets have three anomalous zones: in the magnets themselves and between the magnets (dark stripes in Fig. 2.1A). Inside the magnet, the lines of force of the magnetic field are strictly parallel to each other and always have opposite directions compared to the external lines of force of the sides.

When two magnets come into contact with the same poles (**B**), their magnetic fields do not merge, but create a zone of curvature and compaction of magnetic fields.

In this zone, the intensity of magnetic fields is very high and an external anomalous area is formed (a vertical dark strip in Fig. 2.1B), which is characterized by an increasing level of influence on elementary particles. When passing in a horizontal plane through the anomalous area, the neutrino experiences a vortex effect and is subjected, literally, to “tumbling”.

The influence of the magnetic field occurs only at the level of elementary particles by orienting them with their poles, like a compass needle. The magnetic field of a permanent magnet excites neutrinos that pass through the body of a permanent magnet and causes them to change direction. As a result, neutrino fluxes narrow and expand, forming fluxes of increased and reduced density.

Using the example of experiments with permanent magnets, we consider such properties of magnets.

First, let's check the behavior of a conventional compass under the influence of the Earth's magnetic field. We use the compass for its intended purpose in a strictly horizontal position to the surface of the Earth, then it regularly shows the direction "north-south". If in this direction we turn the compass 90 degrees so that the direction "north-south" remains parallel to the surface of the Earth, and the direction "east-west" is vertical ("east" below), we find a noticeable deviation of the compass needle. In this position, the compass needle shows the division of the device "northeast", that is, it will deviate from the horizontal position down by 45 degrees towards the "north". If, further, we turn the compass 90 degrees along the horizontal plane (“north” towards the west), then we will find that the arrow of the device cannot occupy a certain direction at all.

What's this? The vagaries of a magnetic storm, or there is some kind of regularity in this.

This - is a pattern and indicates the presence of a gravitational basis for the influence of a magnetic field. Earth's gravity has exactly the "southeast" orientation, tending to balance the arrow of the magnet at an angle to the earth's surface.[4]

2.3. Magnetic domains

It is known that in magnetic crystals the magnetic moments of atoms are aligned in such a way that the crystal has a spontaneous magnetization \mathbf{J} oriented along certain crystallographic axes - easy magnetization axes. There may be several or just one. In the latter case, the crystal is called magnetically uniaxial. If the magnetic moments of the atoms (like small magnetic arrows) are aligned in the same direction, the sample, like a permanent magnet, has maximum magnetic energy. This situation is unstable - all natural processes go in the direction of reducing energy. Therefore, a domain structure arises in the sample - a macroscopic system of regions (domains) with different orientations of the vectors \mathbf{J} , so that the entire sample as a whole turns out to be non-magnetic. We called the described excited state of the multidomain magnetic

medium the anger state (from the English anger state - a strongly irritated, angry state).

The phenomenon was discovered in 1998 and is being actively studied today. The experimental and theoretical results of its study are summarized in the work of the remarkable scientist G.S. Kandaurova.

Figure 2.2a shows a multi-turn dynamic helical domain, similar in shape to the Archimedean spiral, in a $(\text{YSm})_3(\text{FeGa})_5\text{O}_{12}$ film 5 mkm thick, in a symmetrical meander-type field with an amplitude of 40 E and a frequency of 300 Hz. Figure 2.2-b shows a multi-turn corrugated helical dynamic domain in a $(\text{YLuBi})_3(\text{FeGa})_5\text{O}_{12}$ film 9.5 mkm thick in an alternating harmonic field with an amplitude of 43 E and a frequency of 3 kHz.

Helical domains in different samples can be very different from each other. For example, these can be exceptionally beautiful spirals, almost perfectly shaped (Fig. 2.2a) or very elegant spirals with corrugated turns (Fig. 2.2b).

The spiral dynamic domains shown in Figure 2.3 in a $(\text{YSm})_3(\text{FeGa})_5\text{O}_{12}$ ferrite-garnet film in a meander-type alternating field with a frequency of 300 Hz and an amplitude of 80 E, photographed from the same place of the sample sequentially with

an interval of less than one minute (a , b, c) show the dynamics of domain development. Further, we do not change anything, we only observe in the microscope the same place of the film in the field, the frequency and amplitude of which (H , f) correspond to the

region of the anger state. Here, on a gray background, a large helical domain appeared (Fig. 2.3A). It behaves like a "live" - its coils oscillate and change their configuration. This can be seen from the gray halo around the black and white coils. Having existed for a

time T_g , the domain quickly disappears. Again, only the gray background is visible. However, after a time T_w , two helical domains appear at the same place in the sample (Fig. 2.3B) with the same twist (the same topological charges). After living through the time T_g , they disappear, and two other spirals appear through T_w (Fig. 2.3B). Now the domains have different charges.

The thickening of the turns shows that in the first (Fig. 2.3B) and in the second (Fig. 2.3C) case, the helical domains compress each other. The maximum values of the characteristic "lifetime" T_g and "waiting" T_w are 10-30 seconds at a field frequency of 200 Hz and sharply decrease with increasing frequency. It is not possible to predict exactly which helical domains will arise: this process is random.

Remember back in school, in physics lessons, we studied the structure of the nucleus: the proton - positively charged and the orbit of electrons - negatively charged particles revolving around the nucleus. For all elements, the proton is stationary. And only a few elements have other properties and a proton nucleus, these are materials that have magnetic properties. Namely: iron, cobalt, nickel (and only that through which an electric current is passed), and ferrites and their alloys.

The modern explanation of this fact is as follows: above the surface of the proton of the listed elements, the spins carrying energy move in the opposite direction from the rotation of electrons. But this statement is identical to the fact that the proton itself rotates with positive charges above its surface, and the charges, of course, close the space, forming a series of magnetic fields.

And if we compare the proton core with a star, then the processes of obtaining energy and converting such charges in the field are identical. (The development of this approach makes it possible to build a model as a structure formed by a four-dimensional substance). This means that the assertion of more ancient philosophers about space and energy as a single structure is not ephemeral, and it must be understood literally. Closing the space with our charges, we break the balance of forces and thus release the energy of the space limited by such circles. And the energy embedded there is of a different level and higher than that which we use. The space is able to replenish any image of the lost charge and continue its further movement.[6]

2.4. The mechanism of formation of magnetic waves in domains

Figure 2.4 shows the magnetic domains on a TbGdFeCo film. A film 180 nm thick was deposited on a glass substrate with 100 nm chromium at a temperature of 200°C and under pressure in argon using magnetron sputtering. Similar multilayer films have been used in the Bose-Einstein condensing of rubidium atoms on an atomic chip.[7]

The molecule that makes up the domains of a magnet is complex and includes iron and rare earth elements. Perhaps the structure of such a complex molecule with the participation of iron is due to the peculiarity of the bond between atoms. The connection of the iron atom with other atoms in the molecule is in an unstable position (Figure 2.5). As shown in the figure, the valence electron (red circle in Fig. 2.5A) from the orbit of the iron atom makes a periodic transition to the orbit of the oxygen atom (O_1). Oxygen, after attaching an electron, expands its orbit, which is accompanied by the emission of a magnetic wave. After some time, the electron from the orbit of oxygen (O_1) returns to the orbit of the iron atom (Fig. 2.5B). Now the iron atom unleashes a magnetic wave. Further, this cycle will continue with the transition of the electron (Fig. 2.5C) to the atom of the next oxygen (O_2), followed by the reverse transition to the iron atom. At the same time, the electron transition occurs only inside the molecule, and therefore,

the electron current between the molecules is not formed. As a result, the orbits of atoms in a molecule undergo expansion and contraction. This process is accompanied by the formation of magnetic waves around the atoms.

Magnetic waves pass through other atoms and molecules, exciting them to transfer electrons within the atoms. This process is damped and periodic, but the presence of many domains in a permanent magnet allows you to maintain the constant presence of the magnetic field as a whole.

The image of magnetic domains (Fig. 2.4) resembles a great creation of nature - the convolutions of the human brain. What are the similarities between them? It is possible that in both materials the convolutions play the same role - the transformation

of magnetic waves. The shapes of the convolutions contribute to the formation of magnetic vortices around themselves, which, in turn, contribute to a change in the density of the neutrino flows passing through them.

As a result, zones of weak compression and expansion are formed in the domains and in some areas of the cerebral cortex, which contribute to the emergence and irritation of the general magnetic field.

If registration and transformation of magnetic waves occur in these materials, then this is the basis of the process of registration of neutrino waves. In the first case, the magnetic domains on the magnetic film change and register magnetic waves. At the same time, passing neutrino flows are refracted and provide the effect of attraction or repulsion. In the second case, the human brain cortex, possibly, registers the neutrino flows directly passing through itself, thereby reading the information they carry from the great gyrus of our planet - the ionosphere.

Perhaps the size and shape of the convolutions of the brain play an important role - this is the password and login, instead of those taken, to enter the main information bank. After all, the human brain, unlike the brain of other living beings, never matches the frequency and size of the convolutions with others.

If a process occurs in the domains of a magnet that causes the birth of a magnetic field, we must look for the cause of such a phenomenon in the structure of the domain

atom itself. Unfortunately, no one has looked inside the atom, so we can imagine the structure of the atom and all the processes occurring in it only hypothetically.

III. Interaction of a magnetic field with neutrino fluxes

A thousand paths lead to error. To the truth - only one.

Jean Jacques Rousseau

3.1. Changing the direction of neutrino flows in a magnet

The effect of attraction and repulsion of two magnets occurs due to the interactions of neutrinos with each other. Neutrinos (ν), as you know, have the ability to penetrate any body, are evenly distributed in all corners of the universe and fly in various directions.

Thus, a permanent magnet is pierced in different directions by neutrinos (ν) flying towards each other, which, falling into the zone of action of the magnetic field, are strictly oriented in the magnetic

field. When passing through a magnet, in planes parallel and perpendicular to the magnetic field, the motions of neutrinos become strictly parallel. In the body of a permanent magnet, the magnetic field strength reaches its maximum value. In the direction parallel to the magnetic field axis, the neutrino flux density increases and narrows around the center line (**e-f-j-h-m-p**). For comparison - neutrinos in the body of non-magnets pass without changing the direction of movement (Fig. 3.1).

At the same time, neutrinos (ν) entering the magnet from the sides (**a-b**), that is, in the transverse direction to the axial line of the magnetic field, when they penetrate into the magnet body, reorient themselves and make a “somersault” by 180 degrees (Fig. 3.1). The neutrino is rearranged in accordance with the magnetic field lines in the magnet body. Next, the neutrino tends to the shortest path to the axial line of the magnetic field. As a result, despite the different angle of incidence of each neutrino on the side surface of the magnet, the direction of motion of the neutrino in the body of the magnet is strictly perpendicular to the axial line of the magnetic field (**b-c** Fig.3.1).

When leaving the magnet, the neutrino (\mathbf{v}) again makes a “somersault” and takes the original direction of motion ($\mathbf{c-d}$). This process plays an important role in the properties of a magnet, since it characterizes its ability to displace the neutrino flux over the entire thickness of the magnet.

Neutrinos arriving perpendicular to the surface of the end part of the magnet (\mathbf{v}) and having a parallel direction to the magnetic field lines penetrate the magnet without changing direction ($\mathbf{a-b}$ in Fig. 3.2A).

Neutrinos arriving perpendicular to the surface of the end part of the magnet (\mathbf{v}) and having a parallel direction to the magnetic field lines penetrate the magnet without changing direction ($\mathbf{a-b}$ in Fig. 3.2A).

However, neutrinos arriving in the direction ($\mathbf{e-c}$) change direction in the magnet in accordance with ($\mathbf{e-h-m-t}$). Neutrinos flying in the direction ($\mathbf{c-e}$) pass along ($\mathbf{c-k-o-p}$). Similarly, neutrinos in the direction ($\mathbf{s-w}$) along the transverse plane of the magnetic field pass along the line ($\mathbf{s-d-u-z}$). The peculiarity of the passage of transverse neutrino flows is that, when crossing a magnet, they necessarily pass along the shortest path (Fig. 3.2B). As a result, the neutrino flux (\mathbf{v}) in the body of the permanent magnet we are considering has only two directions, parallel and perpendicular to the magnetic fields, that is, strictly and mutually perpendicular.

In this regard, a permanent magnet plays the role of a kind of "rectifier" of neutrino fluxes, or acts as an optical prism. Such a change in the direction of neutrino motion (\mathbf{v}) in the body of a permanent magnet forms a total displacement by the thickness of the magnet in the corresponding planes of the magnetic field.

However, the total resultant action of counter-moving neutrinos on a permanent magnet is balanced ($\mathbf{v} + (-\mathbf{v}) = \mathbf{0}$), since the number and direction of neutrinos entering the surface of the magnet ($+\mathbf{v}$) correspond to the number and direction of neutrinos emerging through the magnet ($-\mathbf{v}$), i.e. ($\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}$). The only change is that all neutrinos (\mathbf{v}) undergo a parallel displacement along the planes of the magnet. As a result, all changes in neutrino fluxes occur only in the body of a permanent magnet, and outside

it they retain a uniform distribution as in the surrounding space. Therefore, the magnetic field of one magnet is not capable of creating an effect of attraction and repulsion around itself. For the formation of such effects, it is necessary to have another magnet or an object with a magnetic field.

b) and **(c-d)** in Figure 3.3).

So, in the body of a permanent magnet, the direction of neutrino flows is straightened, as shown in Figures 3.2 and 3.3. However, in the body of the magnet, the neutrino fluxes undergo compression around the axial line under the influence of the intense section of the magnetic field (red arrows **(a-**

Falling with a certain bias on a permanent magnet, neutrinos in the body of the magnet are strictly oriented along the parallel and perpendicular directions of the magnetic flux of the permanent magnet and, when leaving it, restore the original direction in space.

The number and level of the flux density of neutrinos incident on the sides of the magnet **(ac)** and **(bd)**, as well as **(ab)** and **(cd)** are equal and mutually balanced (Fig.3.3).

Such a change in the direction of the neutrino in the body of a permanent magnet or an inductive coil testifies to the susceptibility of the neutrino to displacement under the influence of a magnetic field only in intense sections of the magnetic flux.

As you know, opposite poles of magnets attract. This means that the red pole of the magnetic needle is attracted towards the north pole of the Earth.

This process goes like this. The magnetic waves of the Earth's magnetic field penetrate any body that enters its field. Enveloping a permanent magnet, the Earth's magnetic field interacts with its magnetic field and creates an anomalous zone around it. A potential difference is formed for neutrinos (ν) passing through the magnetic needle and oriented in the Earth's magnetic field, which tends to create an equilibrium position. The resulting potential difference of the neutrino flux ($\Delta\nu$) twists the magnet until the neutrino fluxes are balanced.

The position equal to the minimum value of the potential difference (Δv_{\min}) is achieved with the parallel direction of the magnetic field lines with opposite poles, as shown in Figure 3.4. That's why any permanent magnet in a free state tends to be

oriented along the "north-south" sides. This feature of bodies with the property of a magnet shows that any magnet is influenced by the Earth's magnetic field and, depending on its position in space, creates parallel magnetic fields around it. In

bodies that do not have the property of a magnet, such a process does not occur, and therefore they do not have the ability to navigate in a magnetic field.

The greatest strength of a magnet is found at its poles, and this strength falls off rapidly with increasing distance from the pole. Perhaps this process can be explained by the fact that, leaving the body of the magnet, the neutrino flux scatters and loses density, and the magnetic field strength decreases accordingly. At a point located exactly in the middle between the two poles of a bar magnet (i.e., a magnet made in the form of a strip, bar), the magnetic field reaches its maximum value.

3.2. The mechanism of formation of the magnet attraction effect

When two magnets approach each other with opposite poles, the magnetic fields of both permanent magnets gradually merge, and when the magnets stick, their magnetic fields form one. In this case (Figure 3.5), on opposite poles (N and S) of magnets with sides (a-c) and (b-d), the neutrino flux, when leaving the magnet, enters the outer anomalous zone (M-), where the magnetic field strength is less than in the inner anomalous zone (M+). In the outer anomalous zone (M-), the neutrino flux expands and then passes parallel to the opposite magnet in the expanded position. The densities of neutrino flows going towards each other become unequal, their potentials do not match, resulting in a repulsive effect. The neutrino fluxes (t, n) in Figure 3.5, falling on the left (z-x) outer side of the permanent magnet, when passing through the section (a-b-c-d) between the opposite poles of the magnets, scatter and, when penetrating into the opposite magnet, retain a parallel direction to the magnetic field

lines. Flows of neutrinos (\mathbf{k} , \mathbf{m}) going towards them also expand when they leave the

magnet ($\mathbf{b-d}$) and, when they penetrate into the next magnet ($\mathbf{a-c}$), in such an expanded form, they keep moving parallel to the axial line.

Such an extended

position of the opposing neutrino flows creates a difference in their potentials ($\mathbf{F}_1-\mathbf{F}_2$) in each magnet, and both magnets are attracted relative to each other.

When opposite poles of a permanent magnet approach, the inclined neutrino fluxes (\mathbf{t} , \mathbf{n}) and (\mathbf{k} , \mathbf{m}) incident on the outer left ($\mathbf{z-x}$) and right ($\mathbf{u-h}$) sides of the magnets align their directions in the magnet body in parallel and shrink closer to the center line magnetic field.

This process is the primary alignment or internal compaction of neutrino flows ($+\mathbf{v}\rho^+$), since these neutrino flows are compressed and pass parallel to the axial line of the longitudinal magnetic field. When crossing and getting into the external anomalous zone of the magnetic field ($\mathbf{M-}$), formed between the magnets, this neutrino flux changes its density in the direction of decrease. This process can be called secondary alignment or external rarefaction of neutrino flows ($-\mathbf{v}\rho^-$). This neutrino flux, when it hits the next magnet, retains such a discharged density and passes in a discharged state. We will call this process tertiary alignment or internal rarefaction of neutrino flows ($+\mathbf{v}\rho^-$).

Total Strength

$$\mathbf{F}_1 = (+\mathbf{v}\rho^+) + (-\mathbf{v}\rho^-) + (+\mathbf{v}\rho^-) = (-\Delta\mathbf{v}\rho),$$

where ρ - is the neutrino flux density.

As a result, the level of the neutrino flux density after the secondary alignment weakens and a potential difference ($-\Delta\mathbf{v}\rho$) is formed between the magnets, creating a repulsive or attractive effect of the magnets.

$$\mathbf{F}_2 = (+\mathbf{v}\rho^+) + (-\mathbf{v}\rho^-) + (+\mathbf{v}\rho^-) = (-\Delta\mathbf{v}\rho)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_1 + \mathbf{F}_2 = (-\Delta\mathbf{v}\rho) + (-\Delta\mathbf{v}\rho) = -2(\Delta\mathbf{v}\rho)$$

Another important change in the neutrino pressure potentials occurs precisely in the area (a-b-c-d), as shown by the dark triangles in Figure 3.5, between the opposite poles of the magnets. Neutrino fluxes (e) entering the side surface of the magnet at a smaller angle $\leq \alpha$ cannot exert pressure on the inner side of the opposite magnet (b-d). All neutrino fluxes of the (r-i) type, falling on the sides of both magnets and logically crossing the end sides of the magnets (a-c) and (b-d) remain not involved in creating counteraction F_1 and F_2 .

In his treatise on electricity and magnetism, Maxwell believes that if the powers of the magnetic poles \mathbf{m}_1 and \mathbf{m}_2 , the distance between them \mathbf{L} and the repulsive force \mathbf{f} are expressed numerically, then

$$\mathbf{f} = \frac{\mathbf{m}_1 \mathbf{m}_2}{l^2}$$

but if (\mathbf{m}), (\mathbf{L}), and (\mathbf{F}) are specific units of magnetic pole, length, and force, then

$$\mathbf{f} [\mathbf{F}] = \left(\frac{\mathbf{m}}{\mathbf{L}}\right)^2 \frac{\mathbf{m}_1 \mathbf{m}_2}{l^2} \quad \text{whence it follows that}$$

$$[\mathbf{m}^2] = [\mathbf{L}^2 \mathbf{F}] = \mathbf{L}^2 \frac{\mathbf{M}\mathbf{L}}{\mathbf{T}^2} \quad \text{or} \quad [\mathbf{m}] = [\mathbf{L}^{3/2} \mathbf{T}^{-1} \mathbf{M}^{1/2}]$$

Therefore, a single pole has a dimension equal to 3/2 in relation to length; in relation to time, a dimension equal to - 1; and in relation to mass, a dimension equal to +1/2; this coincides with the dimension of the electrostatic unit of electricity, established earlier in a completely analogous way.

The accuracy of this law can be considered established by Coulomb's experiments with torsion balances and confirmed by the experiments of Gauss and Weber. So also by all observers in magnetic observatories making daily magnetic measurements and obtaining results which would have to become inconsistent with each other if the law for force were erroneously adopted. Additional confirmation follows from its consistency with the laws of electromagnetic phenomena.[8]

The value of the angle α , which is directly dependent on the distance between the magnets, plays an important role in the formation of the force that pushes the magnets to each other. Neutrino fluxes in the directions (f-p) form a magnet repulsive force, however, it is inversely proportional to the angle α . The total value of all unbalanced neutrino fluxes of type (f-p), (indicated by green dotted lines in Figure 3.5) and formed between two permanent magnets facing each other with opposite poles, depends on the

distance between them. As the magnets approach one by one, the lines of force of their magnetic fields gradually merge. A single whole is formed and the interaction of neutrino flows begins to create a difference in their potentials. The closer the distance between the magnets, the more intense the outer anomalous zone of the magnetic field becomes, which in any case will be less than the intensity level of the inner anomalous zone of the magnetic field. When the distance between the magnets approaches zero, $\alpha = 90^\circ$, the sum of the repulsive neutrino fluxes to the inner sides tends to zero, and the sum of the repulsive neutrino fluxes reaches a maximum and two magnets stick.

About the effect of sticking magnets, Maxwell, in his famous treatise, says this:

If the element $\mathbf{dx dy dz}$ is a particle of a magnet and has the magnetic properties of a magnet having a positive pole power \mathbf{m} and a length \mathbf{ds} . Then at an arbitrary point in space \mathbf{P} , spaced at a distance \mathbf{r} from the positive pole and at a distance \mathbf{r}^1 from the negative one, the magnetic potential \mathbf{V} will consist of the potential $\mathbf{m/r}$ created by the positive pole and the potential $\mathbf{m/r}^1$ created by the negative pole, i.e. .

$$\mathbf{V} = \frac{\mathbf{m}}{\mathbf{r}^1 - \mathbf{r}} \quad (1)$$

If the distance between the poles \mathbf{ds} is very small, one can put

$$\mathbf{r}^1 - \mathbf{r} = \mathbf{ds} \cos \varepsilon$$

where ε is the angle between the vector directed from the magnet to the point \mathbf{P} and the axis magnet. In the limit, we get [13]

$$\mathbf{V} = (\mathbf{m} \mathbf{ds} \cos \varepsilon) \mathbf{r}^2$$

Therefore, we will display the distance between the magnets through the coefficient $\cos \alpha$. Then one can easily calculate the level of the neutrino flux density in the case of attachment of permanent magnets with cross sections of 1 cm^2 . If, using dynamometry, we measure the physical force of attraction between two permanent magnets with a cross section of 1 cm^2 , then using the following formula, we can determine the density level of the oblique neutrino flux:

$$\mathbf{F} = \cos \alpha \cdot 1 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \nu \mu \quad (2)$$

where $\cos \alpha$ is the ratio of the thickness of the magnets, equal to 1 cm , to the distance between the magnets. When magnets stick, $\cos \alpha = \cos 0 = 1$,

μ - magnetic constant, \mathbf{F} - determined physically,

ν - density level of the oblique neutrino flux.

From here we calculate the level of the neutrino flux density in one square centimeter, taking into account the fact that both magnets experience the neutrino force:

$$\nu_{\text{min}} = F / 2\cos\alpha \cdot 1 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \mu \quad (3)$$

In this position, that is, when the magnets stick with opposite pole sides, the forces of the neutrino flows F_1 and F_2 pushing both magnets act only in directions

opposite to each other. Due to the fact that the distance between the magnets is zero, the balancing forces will disappear on the opposite inner sides of the magnets (**B-C**) and (**E-R**) (Fig. 3.6). Only the forces of the neutrino fluxes F_1

and F_2 remain, which decrease their density in opposite magnets.

As a result, there will be an effect of attraction of opposite poles (**S** and **N**) of magnets, generated under the action of neutrinos (Fig. 3.6). In the effect of attraction of opposite poles of magnets, an important role is played by the neutrino flux incident on the inner sides of the magnets. The absence of longitudinal neutrino flows in the inner sides of the magnets creates a potential difference for the neutrino flows coming from the outer sides of the magnet.

The neutrino fluxes of the transverse direction (**1-2**) and (**5-3**), incident on the horizontal sides of the magnets, play a specific role - the displacement of the direction of the inclined neutrino fluxes over the entire thickness of the magnet (**1-2-3-4**) and (**5-3-2-6**).

As stated above, when two permanent magnets with opposite poles (**S** and **N**) approach, a potential difference occurs for inclined neutrino fluxes that fall on the entire area of the side sections and cross in the direction (red small dotted lines in Figure 3.7) the inner sides of the permanent magnets.

However, they (**B, D, C, E**) pass in the transverse direction (marked with blue bold dotted arrows in Figure 3.7) and are balanced when exiting on the other side by

neutrino flows going towards. Lateral inclined neutrino fluxes, penetrating into the permanent magnet, cross the magnet strictly across, which will lead to their

displacement through the entire thickness of the permanent magnet. This offset results in no repulsive force on the opposing magnet in the area marked with the red dotted line.

As a result, between the two magnets, a potential difference is formed between the counterflows of neutrinos (**B-C**) and (**D-E**), the density level, which directly depends on the angle α .

In a permanent magnet, the level of magnetic field strength reaches its maximum value in the body of the magnet, that is, around the central axial line of the magnet and forms an internal anomalous magnetic zone.

In the inner anomalous zone (**M+**) of the first magnet, the neutrino fluxes are strongly compacted (**vp+**), and in the next magnet they are also strongly expanded (**vp-**). It should be noted here that in the outer

anomalous magnetic zone (**M-**) the neutrino fluxes expand after passing through the magnet and create a certain potential difference in the next magnet (Fig. 3.5).

In the absence of an opposing permanent magnet, the side streams of neutrinos (**C** and **E**) are balanced by the opposite streams of neutrinos (**B** and **D**) (marked with red dotted arrows in Fig. 3.8).

Any body that does not have a magnetic field meets indifference from the magnet. This circumstance indicates that one magnet and its magnetic field, without taking into account the weak magnetic field of the Earth, does not have the property of attraction and repulsion. This property of it is manifested due to the influence of neutrinos only at the sites of magnetic field anomalies. The adhesion of iron to a magnet can be explained by the fact that the crystal structure of the former allows the excitation of a consistent secondary magnetic field in its structure, as a result of which it is obligatory,

and only attracted to the magnet. In fact, any magnet on the surface of the Earth is in interaction with the magnetic field of our planet and is in a state of active background interaction.

3.3. The mechanism of formation of the effect of repulsion of magnets

When two magnets with the same poles (**N** and **N**) approach each other (Fig. 3.9), their magnetic fields are compressed and distorted. In this zone, the magnetic fields of permanent magnets, as it were, tumble, and an alternating process occurs. Here, oriented neutrinos are consistently flipped 180° and grouped into a narrow beam. It is on this beam that the level of neutrino flux density is high. The beam density exceeds the counterflow of neutrinos of lower density. As a result, a difference in their potentials is formed (bold red arrows in Fig. 3.9).

Between the same poles (**N** and **N**) of two permanent magnets, the carriers of magnetic fields move towards each other, and therefore the sequence of magnetic fields does not match. In the process of further approach of these magnets to each other, compression and curvature of the magnetic fields and the transition of the magnetic field carrier from one field to another occur. In this case, the transition of the carrier - neutrino occurs abruptly, with a sharp change in the direction of movement and a compressed deformation of the magnetic field lines. As a result, an external anomalous magnetic zone (**M-**) is formed between the magnets, which is similar to the anomalous zone in the magnet body, but has a sign-variable and lower density level.

Neutrino flows parallel to the longitudinal magnetic field and going towards each other behave differently in the anomalous zone. Inclined neutrino fluxes (**k,m**) and (**t,s**) in Figure 3.9, falling on the right and left outer sides of the permanent magnets, when passing the section (**a-b**) and (**c-d**) between the same poles of the magnets, undergo compression. After penetrating into the next magnet, they maintain a parallel direction to the magnetic field lines and consistently change direction in the direction of compression. When entering the anomalous zone (**M-**), the fluxes of these neutrinos are focused around the axial line of the magnetic field and continue to move along the axial line (thin dotted arrows in Figs. 3.9 and 3.10).

Oblique neutrino fluxes (ν) incident on the outer left and right sides of the permanent magnets align their directions in the magnet body in parallel and are

compressed closer to the axial line of the magnetic field. We have already called this process the primary alignment or internal

compaction of neutrino flows ($+\nu\rho^+$), since these neutrino flows are compressed and pass parallel to the axial line of the longitudinal magnetic field. When crossing and entering the outer anomalous zone (M^-) of the magnetic field, this neutrino flux changes its density towards compaction. This process can be called secondary equalization or external compaction of neutrino flows ($-\nu\rho^+$).

Further, the compacted neutrino flux, when it hits the next magnet, retains such a maximum density. We call this process tertiary alignment or internal compaction of neutrino flows ($+\nu\rho^+$). As a result, the level of the neutrino flux density after the secondary alignment increases and a potential difference ($+\Delta\nu\rho$) is formed between the magnets, creating a repulsive effect of the magnets.

$$\mathbf{F}_1 = (+\nu\rho^+) + (-\nu\rho^+) + (+\nu\rho^+) = (+\Delta\nu\rho)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_2 = (+\nu\rho^+) + (-\nu\rho^+) + (+\nu\rho^+) = (+\Delta\nu\rho)$$

where ρ -is the neutrino flux density.

Both forces have a positive potential, the sum of which exceeds the forces \mathbf{F}_1 and \mathbf{F}_2 applied at the ends of the magnets. The total force with the same poles of the magnets is always greater than the forces on the outskirts, which leads to the repulsion of the magnets:

Both forces have a positive potential, the sum of which exceeds the forces applied at the ends of the magnets. The total force with the same poles of the magnets is always greater than the forces on the outskirts, which leads to the repulsion of the magnets:

$$\mathbf{F}_1 + \mathbf{F}_2 = (+\Delta\nu\rho) + (+\Delta\nu\rho) = +2(\Delta\nu\rho)$$

This position of the direction of the indicated neutrino flows creates a large potential difference only around the axial line. Their sum generates a significant force that repels both magnets from each other. In one, whole magnet, the unequal potential of countercurrent parallel neutrino flows creates a stressed state in the magnet itself. Such a state of counterflows of high-density neutrinos constantly creates a stressed state inside the magnet, and when the integrity of the magnet is broken, a repulsive effect occurs at the fault site.

Inclined neutrino flows, when falling on the outer vertical sides of the magnets, will be focused on parallel streams, which, when leaving the inner vertical sides of the magnets, are refocused (small dotted

arrows in Fig. 3.10).

Oblique neutrino fluxes (**a,b**) and (**c,m**) falling on the horizontal sides of the magnets and which, upon exiting, fall into the outer zone of the magnetic anomaly, are also focused on the inner vertical side of the magnet (dashed arrows in Fig. 3.10). It is these neutrino flows create an additional element of the repulsion effect.

The main change in neutrino pressure potentials occurs precisely in the area (**a-b-c-d**), as shown by the blue triangles in Figure 3.9, between the same poles of the magnets. Neutrino fluxes (**a**), falling on the horizontal surface of the magnet at a smaller angle $\leq \alpha$, can exert pressure on the opposite inner vertical side of the magnet (**b-d**).

At the same time, the neutrino fluxes (**r-i**) in Figure 3.9, falling on the horizontal sides of both magnets and logically crossing the inner vertical sides of the magnets (**a-c**), (**b-d**) remain without opposing neutrino fluxes. The value of the angle α , which is directly dependent on the distance between the magnets, plays an important role in the formation of the force that repels the magnets from each other. Neutrino fluxes in the directions (**f-p**) form a repulsive force for magnets, but it is inversely proportional to the angle α .

And so, as shown in Figure 3.11, let's schematically trace the path (green dotted line) of inclined neutrinos falling on the horizontal side of the magnet (**AB**). A neutrino falling from point **1** to point **2** penetrates the magnet to point **3**. Then, under the influence of an intense magnetic field in the outer anomalous zone, it changes direction and falls to point **4** on the inner vertical side (**ET**) of the magnet. Having penetrated into the magnet, the neutrino passes parallel to the magnetic field line up to point **5** and, upon exiting from the outer vertical side (**KH**) of the magnet, restores its original direction at point **6**.

Similarly, a neutrino incident (red dotted line) from point **7** to point **8** on the lateral horizontal side (**DC**), passes to point **9** and, under the influence of the magnetic field

of the outer anomalous zone, passes through points **10** and **11**. Then it passes parallel to the lines of force longitudinal magnetic field and at the exit restores the direction of the original movement **12** and **13**.

The total value of all unbalanced neutrino fluxes (Δv) formed between two permanent magnets facing each other with the same poles depends on the distance between them. When the magnets approach, the tension in the anomalous magnetic zone increases, the streams of lateral inclined neutrinos, which repel the magnets from each other, become more focused. When the distance between the magnets approaches zero, $\alpha = 90^\circ$, the density of the repulsive neutrino flows reaches a maximum, pushing the two magnets harder.

When the like poles (**S** and **S**) of the magnets approach, a compressed and deformed outer anomalous zone (**M-**) is formed. When passing through this zone, the neutrino, as an elementary particle with $1/2$ spin, changes the direction of its movement by 180° (Fig. 3.10). The rotation, in this case, occurs in concert, that is, the neutrino flux beam narrows around the center line, where its density level increases several times. When an opposing permanent magnet penetrates the body, this neutrino beam creates a repulsive effect.

An important principle in the repulsive effect is the formation of a deformed outer anomalous zone, where the neutrino is forced to make a somersault and change the direction of motion. It is this property of the neutrino that determines the property of a permanent magnet to narrow neutrino fluxes into a beam.

Neutrinos change their direction under the influence of a magnetic field. If the magnetic fields of two magnets do not coincide in their directions, the parallelism of their flow is violated, which inevitably leads to a displacement of the planes of the magnetic fields and the alienation of their carriers. In such

positions between both magnets, forces of attraction and repulsion are simultaneously formed, mutually equal in potential.

Two permanent magnets placed at 90 degrees to each other receive a shift in magnetic fields. As a result, “zones of magnetic silence” are formed around the permanent magnet at certain angles (dotted circle in Fig. 3.12), which are not subject to the effects of attraction and repulsion. In the zones of magnetic silence, the balanced state of the counterflows of neutrinos provides a mutually balanced counteraction of the transverse and longitudinal magnetic fields. Their potential is zero, that is, there is no effect of attraction and repulsion of other permanent magnets.

IV. Changes in the direction of neutrinos between magnetic fields

There is nothing more dangerous to a new truth than an old error.
Johann Goethe

4.1. Neutrinos in the formation of magnetic field lines

The space in which some forces act is commonly called a force field. The force field has a beginning and an end, respectively, the direction of action. Thus, around a magnet we have a force magnetic field, just as around a body charged with electricity, we have an electric field. We represent any magnetic field as consisting of a large number of magnetic lines of force. They leave one pole of the magnet and enter the

other pole. At the same time, it is generally accepted that the lines of force have a direction from the north pole of the magnet to its south pole (Fig. 4.1).

Magnetic lines of force that have the same direction repel each other. Lines directed in different directions are attracted to each other.

The magnetic field does not have the property and force of attraction. It only contributes to the orientation and change in the direction of movement of elementary particles in space.

The effect of magnetic attraction and repulsion is formed as a result of the influence of a magnetic field on a neutrino, by expanding or compacting the neutrino flows passing through it. Neutrinos (ν) are quantized and after leaving the permanent magnet, oscillating the magnetic wave, form lines of force around the magnet.

A line of force, or an integral curve, is a curve, the tangent to which at any point

coincides in direction with the vector, which is an element of the vector field at the same point. It is used to visualize vector fields that are difficult to visualize in any other way. In Fig.4.2, the force field of the magnet is visualized with iron filings.

According to the chemical composition, magnetite consists of 31% **FeO** and 69% **Fe₂O₃**

When a molecular bond is formed between the atoms of a molecule, the presence of free cells for electrons on the upper electron shell of the atoms allows the appearance of an imbalance in the neutrino force that binds the atoms. As a result, regions with abnormal deviations in the strength of the molecular bond are formed in the molecule. Neutrinos, getting into these zones, change the direction of movement, they are focused. This causes the atom's electron to deviate from its location. The equilibrium of the intraatomic neutrino bond is disturbed, an electron is excited and passes to the upper shell of a neighboring atom.

When the outer electron shell expands, a neutrino wave is formed, which creates a wave effect responsible for the formation of a magnetic field. Neutrino waves leave the atom, creating magnetic waves. The farther neutrino waves are scattered from the

magnet, the density of neutrino fluxes decreases, and the power of magnetic waves weakens accordingly. The flux density of magnetic waves at equal distances forms a kind of line that coincides with the lines of force of the magnetic field, which, having made a certain circle, closes. Thus, the formation of a magnetic field begins.

In a solenoid, this process happens a little differently. When electricity passes through a conductor, an electron sequentially passes from one atom to another. Such a transition forms an expansion and contraction of the electron shell of atoms, which is accompanied by the formation of neutrino waves. In these zones, the neutrino flux changes its oscillation frequency and forms a wave flux. This sequence is due to the process of electron release itself.

Consider the mechanism for generating electric current in a generator. When the rotor is forced to rotate, anomalous magnetic zones are formed between the moving magnets. Neutrino fluxes, falling into these zones, change their density, respectively, there will be a force acting on the nucleus of an atom of magnets. As a result, the core of the conductor between the magnets begins to oscillate (Fig. 4.3), periodically

pressing on the wall of its own electron shells. When the pressure of the nucleus is strong, a free electron jumps out of the electron shell and passes to the electron shell of another atom. A series current of electrons is formed,

which, by means of free electrons in the metal, begins to propagate in the direction of atoms with a free cell of electrons.

The transition of an electron from the shell of one atom to another shell of a neighboring atom and its return back occurs in the zone of forced oscillation of the magnetic field. Beyond this zone of magnetic coercion, only neutrino oscillations are propagated, and electrons oscillate within the limits of the atom's own electron shell. In an alternating current network, an electron oscillates 50 times per second. In this case, the electron changes its polarity each time, moving from an electron to a positron and back.

The frequency of the neutrino quantum oscillation (ν) is strictly proportional to its own oscillation length and mass, and generally forms a vacuum. Naturally, this

frequency must be no less than and a multiple of the Compton frequency. Thus, the following relationship holds for the "neutrino momentum":

$$\omega_{\nu} = \frac{2\pi mc^2}{h} \quad [c^{-1}]$$

where m is the neutrino mass generating vacuum quanta, h is Planck's constant, c is the speed of light in vacuum.

Neutrino (ν) is quantized, in the absence of energy exchange with counter-going neutrinos, exerts pressure. When penetrating into denser bodies, it changes direction. All these properties of neutrinos are preserved everywhere.

The neutrino interaction is the only Fermi field known to us, which is simple and fundamental. Known properties of neutrinos, more and more, occupy a central place in elementary particle physics and become the most relevant and promising direction.

The magnet is a complex alloy of metals (ferrite garnet $(YSm)_3(FeGa)_5O_{12}$ and $(YLuBi)_3(FeGa)_5O_{12}$), in the molecule of which unstable electrons are stored on the electron shell. An unstable electron in a molecule is located in an iron atom and makes a transition inside the molecule from an iron atom to an oxygen atom and vice versa. All these transitions are accompanied by the participation and excitation of an electron neutrino, which is reflected in neutrino fluxes around the ferrite molecule.

The permanent magnet is a neutrino flux converter. When the neutrino passes in the direction of the longitudinal axis of the magnet, the neutrino flux experiences compression and compaction. In this state, the neutrino flux crosses the magnet along the shortest path.

Figure 4.4 schematically shows how neutrinos pass through a magnet. Neutrinos $1_1, 2_1, 3_1, 4_1$ before penetrating the magnet had directions at a certain angle. However, from the moment they penetrate the magnet, they move only parallel to the axis of the magnet. When leaving the magnet, neutrinos $1_2, 2_2, 3_2, 4_2$ restore their original direction of motion. This is one of the important properties of neutrinos. Such a zigzag path makes a neutrino only in a permanent magnet or in a solenoid. The figure shows

the movement of neutrinos only in one direction. In fact, the same neutrino movements (ν) occur in the opposite direction, and these interactions of neutrinos as a whole on the magnet are balanced.

The neutrino (ν) at the suppression of the magnet has another unique property. This property of the neutrino gives the magnet its main and important quality. When crossing a magnet, after colliding with a ferrite atom, the neutrino makes a certain oscillation corresponding to the magnetic wave. Leaving the body of the magnet, neutrinos propagate, preserving the received oscillation. The frequency of this magnetic oscillation is between the frequencies of x-rays and ultraviolet radiation. This magnetic oscillation has a tangible effect on free elementary particles.

The exciters of the magnetic field in the permanent magnet and the solenoid are different sources. It is in a permanent magnet - magnetic domains, in a solenoid - moving electrons. In both cases, these sources are mutually exclusive: there is no electron current in a permanent magnet, and there are no magnetic domains in a solenoid. At the same time, both sources create the same magnetic fields, with the same properties. This circumstance indicates that the mechanism of formation of the magnetic field is hidden more deeply and is hidden at the level of the atom.

Experiments with magnets show that the force of attraction and repulsion in the vertical position of the magnets is less than when the magnets are located horizontally. The anomalous magnetic field plays the main role in changing the direction of neutrino flows.

These statements indicate that the magnetic field plays a major role in the orientation of neutrinos and elementary particles. A magnet in the path of the neutrino flow plays the same role as a transparent prism in the path of the light flow. Anomalous phenomena in a magnetic field create the same anomalous phenomena in a stream of elementary particles.

When the attraction effect is formed, oblique neutrino fluxes incident on the outer sides pass only one stage of focusing, that is, compression.

With the repulsion effect, the flows pass through two stages of focusing (double compression). In the formation of the repulsion effect, the main role is played by oblique neutrino fluxes emerging from the transverse sides of the magnet and falling

into the outer zone of the magnetic anomaly. They, falling into the inner longitudinal sides of the magnets, create a repulsive effect.

This is how the properties of permanent magnets and inductive magnetic coils are formed.

All physical properties of magnets are connected with the movements of neutrino flows. The magnetic field is a space filled with oscillatingly moving neutrino flows. Electromagnetic waves are neutrino oscillations, that is, neutrino waves.

4.2. Passage of neutrinos in magnets of various shapes

The property of a permanent magnet to create a magnetic field around itself can completely repeat the solenoid. When an electric current passes through the winding of the solenoid, a magnetic field is formed around it. The magnetic field formed in this way has all the properties of the magnetic field of a permanent magnet, which gives reason to assume that the carrier of these magnetic fields is identical (Fig. 4.5). Despite the fact that a magnetic field is formed in the solenoid parallel to the axial line of the solenoid, attraction and repulsion effects can also form between them.

This fact indicates that these effects do not depend on the density and composition of the material of the magnetic field source. A magnet or solenoid, with one dipole magnetic field, is able to change the motion of neutrinos in directions parallel and perpendicular to the axial line of the magnetic field.

Unlike a rectangular magnet, in a solenoid, as shown in Figure 4.5, the longitudinal passage of a neutrino (**a-x-c-d**) occurs only through the axial line of the magnetic field (**m-o-h**) and provides the smallest distance between opposite points of the surface solenoid (**a-x-b-r**). This principle of passage of neutrinos through the solenoid is due to their suppression of the magnetic field in the shortest way.

Figure 4.6 shows the dipole magnetic field of a spherical permanent magnet. Here,

too, the double direction of intersection of neutrino fluxes perpendicular to each other is preserved. Calculations show that the number and directions of neutrino fluxes incident on the surface of a spherical magnet correspond to the outgoing fluxes, as a result of which internal and external equilibrium in the magnet is maintained.

In a ring magnet, an external anomalous zone of the magnetic field is formed in the center of the magnet. It is characterized by the fact that the inner part of the ring magnet is one polarity, between which a repulsive effect appears. When passing through this anomalous zone (A Fig.4.7), the neutrino flux narrows, condensing its density. At the exit from the ring magnet, the neutrino flux restores its former density.

If the hypothesis about the refraction of neutrino flows in

the body of a magnet is correct, then the shape and direction of the polarity of the magnet play an important role in the manifestation of the effects of attraction and repulsion of magnets. You can find the optimal shape of the magnet, where the axial direction of the magnetic field differs from the correct shape. Then, the neutrino flows crossing the magnet will not be balanced at the exit from it. In this case, it is possible to create a form of a magnet that upsets the balance of countercurrent neutrino flows, as a result, it cannot assume a state of rest in space. Such a magnet will always be directed to the side where the flow of counter-moving neutrinos cannot form a reaction.

The optimal theoretical form of a magnet that provides this effect is a cone-shaped disk, as shown in its section in Figure 4.8, with a hole in the middle and magnetized from the

edge to the middle of the disk in a horizontal position. Unfortunately, it is very difficult to create such a magnet, since its magnetization requires special technologies and equipment.

In such a conical disk, the streams of neutrinos directed to create opposition to each other will be focused in such a way that their natural balance is disturbed. As a result, the total force of opposing neutrino flows will be taken outside the magnet body and acted outside the magnet. The disturbed balance of the acting forces from the side **(B)** pushes the magnet in the direction where the counteracting force is less. In the specified disk, this side is the conical top of the disk **(A)**. This disk magnet will move in any direction in space forward with side **(A)**. The two discs on the rotor in opposite direction are the basis of the neutrino drive to get the rotary motion.

4.3. Passage of neutrinos between cylindrical magnets

It has been established that the neutrino orients itself with its energy poles in a magnetic field and, when crossing the magnetic field, changes its direction of motion. Such a process is especially often observed when neutrinos cross the anomalous zone of the magnetic field of a permanent magnet. In creating attraction and repulsion effects between two magnets, we considered a permanent magnet with a rectangular shape. Now let's consider magnets of various shapes and determine their influence on the process of passing neutrino flows during the formation of attraction and repulsion effects.

Let's start with cylindrical magnets of different sizes. When approaching them with different poles **(N – S – N)**, an attraction effect is formed between them. This force is due to the formation of external anomalous zones of the magnetic field between the magnets, scattering the neutrino flux. When three magnets, as shown in Fig. 4.9, are put to each other with different poles **(N – S – N)**, the passage of neutrino flows constitutes a cascade expansion (thick red arrows), which enhances the effect of attracting them to the central magnet. At the same time, the formed angles of divergence $\varphi_1 < \varphi_2$ of the flows between **(a-s-b-r)** and **(d-e-y-c)** after the passage of each magnet expands, which leads to a decrease in the flow density.

Such a cascade expansion of neutrino flows during the passage of magnets leads to the fact that each outer magnet around the central magnet tends to take a place on the same line in the opposite section, where the attraction to the central magnet is

greater than in other areas. When one of the outer magnets starts moving around the central magnet, the second outer magnet simultaneously starts moving and stands against the first magnet. This whole process occurs due to a change in the density of penetrating magnets of neutrino fluxes.

When the magnets approach with the same poles (N – N – N), a repulsion effect forms between them. As shown in Fig. 4.9 by dotted blue arrows, the passage of neutrino flows constitutes a cascade compression, which enhances the effect of their repulsion towards the central magnet. At the same time, the formed angles of

divergence $\varphi_1 < \varphi_2$ of the fluxes between (m-h-o-k-r) and (x-u-y-t-z) after passing each magnet narrows, which leads to an increase in the density of neutrino fluxes.

The cascade compression of magnetic fluxes between three magnets with the same poles leads to the fact that the third magnet, regardless of the pole, will be repelled from the central magnet. To test this effect, to a magnet with an iron object stuck, on the other hand, bring another magnet with the same pole and notice that the iron object will come off the first magnet.

V. The concept and properties of the magnetic field. Conclusions

The signs revealed and established in the course of experiments with permanent magnets indicate that the magnetic field has some regular properties:

- 1) The effect of attraction and repulsion of magnets is strictly related to the interaction of neutrino flows;
- 2) The magnetic field starts from the source of the field, has a direction in the direction of decreasing magnetic field voltage density and ends where the magnetic field density cannot affect elementary particles;

3) Each direction of the magnetic field has an internal anomalous zone in the permanent magnet body. The inner anomalous zone has the highest magnetic field density and its lines of force run parallel;

4) When two magnets with the same poles approach, an external intense anomalous zone is formed between them, where the magnetic fields of the two magnets do not merge, but deform each other. In the outer transverse anomalous zone between them, the lines of force of perpendicular magnetic fields intersect;

5) When two magnets with opposite poles approach, their magnetic fields merge, creating a single magnetic field, while the magnetic field lines in the magnets remain parallel. A longitudinal outer discharged anomalous zone of the magnetic field is created between the magnets;

6) Anomalous zones of magnetic fields of permanent magnets control the direction of neutrino movement. In one individual magnet, this happens only in the inner anomalous zone, where neutrinos move in parallel. In two magnets, depending on the location of the poles, longitudinal and transverse anomalous zones are formed between them. In the longitudinal anomalous zone, the neutrino fluxes expand, and in the transverse anomalous zone they are focused. The effect of attraction and repulsion of two magnets is formed due to the action of streams of neutrinos falling in and out of the sides of opposing magnetic poles;

7) A neutrino incident parallel to the axial line of the magnet, regardless of the angle of incidence on the surface of the magnet, crosses the magnet strictly parallel to the magnetic field lines;

8) A neutrino incident perpendicular to the axial line of the magnet, regardless of the angle of incidence on the horizontal side surface of the magnet, crosses the magnet strictly perpendicular to the lines of force along the shortest path. The number and direction of movement of neutrinos falling and leaving the magnet and passing parallel are always equal and mutually balanced;

9) Changing the direction of neutrino movement along the curve occurs only in the outer anomalous zone of the magnetic field. All neutrino flows, when they enter the internal anomalous zones, move parallel or perpendicular to the lines of force of magnetic fields;

10) In the outer anomalous zone of magnetic fields, formed between the same poles, the neutrino makes a somersault and goes into the opposite magnetic field;

11) Between opposite poles of permanent magnets, neutrino flows align their directions in the magnet body in parallel and are compressed closer to the axial line of the magnetic field. This process is the primary alignment or internal compaction of neutrino flows. When crossing and getting into the external anomalous zone of the magnetic field between the magnets, the neutrino flux changes its density in the direction of decrease. This process is a secondary equalization or external rarefaction of neutrino flows. This neutrino flux, when it hits the next magnet, retains such a discharged density and passes in a discharged state. This process is a tertiary alignment or internal rarefaction of neutrino flows. As a result, the level of the neutrino flux density after the secondary alignment weakens and a potential difference is formed between the magnets, creating a repulsive or attractive effect of the magnets;

12) When approaching two magnets with opposite poles, the number of external oblique neutrino fluxes falling on the surface of the approaching poles is limited. Such a limitation generates a potential difference between the counterflows of neutrinos from the outer poles, as a result of which an additional force is formed that pushes the two magnets to each other;

13) Between the same poles of permanent magnets, neutrino flows align their directions in the magnet body in parallel and are compressed closer to the axial line of the magnetic field. This process is the primary alignment or internal compaction of neutrino flows. When crossing and getting into the external anomalous zone of the magnetic field, the neutrino flux changes its density in the direction of compaction. This process is a secondary alignment or external compaction of neutrino flows. This compacted neutrino flux, when it hits the next magnet, retains this maximum density. This process is a tertiary alignment or internal compaction of neutrino flows. As a result, the neutrino flux density level after the secondary alignment increases and a potential difference is formed between the magnets, creating a repulsive effect of the magnets;

14) When two magnets with the same poles approach, the neutrino fluxes emerging from the sides of the like poles and falling into the outer anomalous zone

change their direction under the influence of magnetic fields and fall on the surface of the approaching sides with the same poles. As a result, a potential difference is formed in the incoming neutrino flows, which generates an additional force of the repulsion effect;

15) Inside the magnet, the lines of force of the magnetic field are strictly parallel to each other and always have opposite directions compared to the external lines of force of the sides;

16) External magnetic field lines are formed as a result of neutrino oscillations at a certain distance from the magnet. Moving away from its source, the magnet, the neutrino flux expands. As a result, the density of neutrino fluxes decreases;

17) The main property of a magnet is the ability to condense or discharge the level of the neutrino flux, which is clearly expressed between two magnets in the form of attraction and repulsion.

V. Magnetic field laws

Figurative and mental modeling of intra-atomic processes gives a vivid idea of the interdependence of the magnetic field and gravity. The magnetic field is a secondary phenomenon and is formed as a result of the excitation of a neutrino and the movement of an electron, while no energy is spent on the formation of a magnetic field. Based on this, the following regularities can be distinguished:

1. The magnetic field is formed by neutrino waves and is not an energy field, it only contributes to the formation of other forces through the interaction of neutrinos;

2. The magnetic field, by itself, cannot affect any particle and matter, except for the neutrino. The magnetic field is created by neutrinos and exists only for neutrinos;

3. The neutrino flux under the influence of a magnetic field narrows and expands. Thus, the neutrino exerts pressure on all material and non-material bodies, including other elementary particles.

Conclusion

Plato - is a friend, but truth is dearer. Aristotle

The mechanism of the influence of a magnetic field on gravity considered in this paper describes well the properties of a magnetic field and determines the role of neutrinos in the formation of a magnetic field. At present, science knows the facts of the influence of the Earth's magnetic field on the elementary particles of the solar wind, which subsequently change their direction and flow around our planet. However, in the history of physics, none of the scientists tried to explain the effects of attraction and repulsion of magnets with the help of flows of elementary particles, including neutrinos. Instead, they were looking for a single particle - the carrier of the magnetic field, which inexplicably pulls the magnets to each other.

The purpose of this work is the theoretical determination of the external properties of the magnetic field and its sources - permanent magnets. This task has been completed and secured by a unique experiment. The nature of the magnetic field and how magnetic waves and lines of force are formed are considered in general terms, which sufficiently explain the mechanism of their occurrence. Perhaps this is far from the ultimate truth. However, the first step has been formed, allowing you to rise and look around: "Is everything the way we thought before?" If someone sees even further with one foot on my step, my task is done.

The effects of attraction and repulsion of permanent magnets, formed with the help of neutrino flows, are successfully used in the operation of electric motors and generators. In these devices, external and internal anomalous zones of permanent magnets and electromagnetic inductive coils are actively used. In anomalous zones, the directions of movement of neutrino flows are bent, which alternately create a magnetic wave. The coordinated arrangement of the sources of magnetic fields - the stator and the rotor, allows them to rotate at a certain frequency. As a result, the electric motor works due to the interaction of neutrino flows, the electromagnetic field only contributes to their curvature. Therefore, it would be more correct if we call the electric motor an electromagnetic-neutrino motor, since the neutrino is the driving force.

In electric generators, the process of formation of an electronic current occurs due to the transfer of electrons from one atom to another atom. Such a process of release of free electrons from atoms, their transition to other atoms often occur as a result of some chemical reactions. However, the release of free electrons in this case differs from the generator process. In a chemical reaction, an electron is released as a result of the decay and formation of new molecules. The intraatomic force is broken, neutrino flows are bent, magnetic waves are formed.

It seems to us that the magnetic field is more visible and more tangible than the gravitational field. We usually say that magnetic storms greatly affect the health of people, especially the sick - "hypertensive". According to the hypothesis of the influence of the magnetic field on gravity, this phenomenon is explained very simply: magnetic storms, or rather magnetic anomalies, form perceptible fluctuations in the level of gravity density on the Earth's surface. Such changes necessarily lead to minor changes in weight and internal capillary blood pressure in the bodies. The blood in the blood vessels of a person becomes heavy or light, respectively, the blood pressure in the vessels will change.

The ability of migratory birds to navigate in space, we refer to their sensitivity to the magnetic field. However, they cannot feel the influence of the magnetic field, since the magnetic field can only interact with iron-containing material, which is almost absent in the body of birds. Birds, while high in the air, may occasionally make a sharp descent, as a result of which they experience a state close to free fall. In this state, the southeast direction of the earth's gravity is clearly felt and the birds check their flight direction relative to the gravitational field. Remember how Galileo threw metal balls from a tower and was surprised that they all fall with some deviation to the southeast.

Living and non-living bodies, in the body or structure of which there is a circular movement of fluid or electrons, are capable of creating a magnetic field around them. Animals and plants, as well as mechanisms in whose organ systems constantly circulate gases and liquids, may create their own magnetic field. As soon as the liquid circulation in the system stops, the magnetic field disappears - the influence of neutrino flows, including gravity, changes. The rest of the bodies in the Earth's magnetic field create some of its curvature through their presence. An interesting example: a dying person

on the scales, after stopping his heart, becomes a few grams lighter, because after stopping his life, the focus of gravity through the body will change.

The magnetic field - is a "magic manager", and the neutrino is an "obedient performer". The neutrino makes a constant oscillation in a certain distance and is quantized. As soon as the oscillation frequency increases, a magnetic field is formed.

We, without realizing it, have been using the services of neutrinos for a long time. To do this, we expend considerable energy to create an external magnetic anomalous zone. Without these conditions, both the engine and the generator will not work.

Experiments with magnets (in Fig. 1.2 and 1.3) clearly indicate the presence of a difference in the fluxes of neutrinos flying in horizontal and vertical directions. Based on these experiments, one can conclude about the mysterious role of the central core of the Earth, the main source of the formation of earth's gravity.

The effects of attraction and repulsion of magnets indicate a change in the direction of neutrino motion. These experiments also confirmed that the magnetic field does not have the property of a direct effect on bodies, and all its imaginary effects occur only through neutrinos. A neutrino can change the direction of its movement, only under the influence of a magnetic field and depending on the strength of the latter, even at relatively small distances.

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They participated in financing the project, their own scientific experiments and in translating scientific works.

They provided computer organizational equipment, reagents, materials, devices, computing resources or other tools for research and experiments. They created conditions for conducting scientific and exploratory work.

By offering our work in an open format to a wide audience, we do not aspire to recognition, academic titles, or awards. But we are confident of one thing: the reader, having gained new knowledge, will thank us for our enormous and unique work.

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In the authorship of the specified scientific works, except for Adayev Ualikhan Zholdasbekovich, Adayev Shokan Ualikhanovich and Adai Marat Ualikhanuly, no one, including scientific institutions, centers and laboratories, has any relation.

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